

Quantitative HRTEM Analysis of Strain Assessment along the Defect Cores in Cryo-rolled CP Ti

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Microscopic and functional manifestation of strains in materials originates from local imperfections in the atomic scale, which essentially depicts shifting of the atom coordinates from their mean equilibrium positions. Hence an estimate of the atomic shift provides the much needed clue to analyze the induced strain in the materials because of defect formation, alloying addition or through metallic deformation. In the present work, a quantitative estimation of strain has been carried out along the defect cores of severely cryo rolled CP Ti from the aberration corrected atomic resolution TEM micrographs.

Image aberration corrected phase contrast micrographs, which are already well analyzed in terms of structural information, are subjected to the investigation of Geometrical Phase Analysis (GPA) to generate the strain map. The map has been normalized with respect to the minimum strain region. Relative variations of strain across the defect cores have been generated. A typical micrograph is shown in fig 1(a). However in the atomic resolution images several linear contrasts can be observed which are postulated to be originated from the accumulation of the localized strain during rolling. Multislice image simulation in a systematic manner has been carried out (fig 1b) to eliminate the effects of defocus, thickness and the alloying elements in the generation of these linear contrasts. Quantitative electron microscopy analyses using the GPA methods are employed to confirm the generation of these linear contrasts due to the localized strains as shown in fig 1(c).

Fig. 1(a-c) Image corrected HRTEM micrograph, corresponding simulated image and the localized strain map from a severely deformed CP Ti specimen.
